

Master Teachers' Leadership Skills, Instructional Competence and Teachers' Performance

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11482726>

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Abstract:

In DepEd's culture, Master Teachers (MTs) are expected to be leaders of learning with a larger and more comprehensive role. They are expected to provide high-quality guidance to students and professional development to career teachers. Along this premise, this correlational study investigated the leadership skills and instructional competence of Master Teachers in relation to teachers' performance in a medium-sized Division in Central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. Data needed for this paper was collected from 204 public elementary school teachers using a self-made instrument that has passed the rigorous tests of validity and reliability. The results revealed that master teachers' leadership skills ($M=4.59$; $SD=0.448$) and their instructional competence ($M=4.68$; $SD=0.410$) were all at very high levels, while teachers' performance was very satisfactory ($m=4.815$). It was also revealed that there was no significant difference ($p=0.562$) in the level of MT's leadership skills. A significant difference ($p=0.050$) was found in the MT's instructional competence level when grouped according to length of service. The study also found no significant relationship between Master Teachers leadership skills and instructional competence with teachers' performance. To address issues identified in this study, various recommendations were provided, among others: Project ECGC (Empathy, Cultural Intelligence, Good Communication and Collaboration and Teamwork), TRAINING PROGRAMS on Continuous Professional Development Master Teachers (CPD); Peer Collaboration and Observation, etc.

Keywords: Master teachers, leadership skills, instructional competence, Silay City, Negros Occidental.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

A Master Teacher's tasks and obligations encompass mentoring, curriculum development, instructional leadership, and the advancement of efficient teaching methods. It describes requirements for Master Teacher advancement, including evaluation of credit points and qualifications. Providing pupils with high-quality instructional competency and career instructors with professional development is the fundamental role of a master teacher. Master Teachers are skilled communicators with great management abilities. They are also competent leaders.

One way to look at teacher effectiveness is as an observable result of students reaching their educational goals in the classroom. MTs positively impact teachers' attitudes and skill sets, including building a solid teaching-learning environment. A successful teaching performance must show a discernible influence on students' learning, as measured by student surveys, pedagogical practices, or student achievement test results. Through supervision and mentoring, competent master teachers impact teachers' performance (Malitic, 2020).

Currently, the tasks associated with planned observation and assessment and offering assistance for curriculum improvement present the greatest challenges to Master Teachers. The perceived intricacy of Master Teachers' roles as instructional leaders and classroom instructors presents some challenges for designing and coordinating teaching tactics and approaches and maintaining a supportive learning environment. The researcher was inspired to perform this investigation by these circumstances and observations.

In identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the MT's instructional supervision and technical assistance skills, this study intends to provide a doable plan to address identified key areas.

Current State of Knowledge

This section tackles present discussions on the leadership skills and instructional competence of Master Teachers in relation to Teachers' Performance. The concepts and study results presented herein will help explain the challenges

and strengths of Master Teachers in carrying their day-to-day work. Mendoza (2022) showed that a school leader's leadership is crucial to the institution's efficacy. The term "instructional leadership" is broad and has many definitions that describe its functions, practices, and results. An effective instructional leader motivates all stakeholders to work toward the school's objectives. In addition, instructional leadership refers to the strategies school leaders use to succeed in teaching-learning.

Every public school in the Philippines is required by Republic Act No. 9155, also known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, Chapter I Sec. 7, Letter E, to have a school head who will collaborate with the teachers to provide exceptional educational projects, programs, and services. This includes a core group of non-teaching staff who will oversee the school's administrative, financial, and auxiliary functions. This explicit legislative provision outlined the duties and obligations of the school principal. The goal is to make the most out of one's leadership abilities. The law allows school administrators to direct instructors and students toward achieving superior learning outcomes. Additionally, it said that school administrators must manage all school-related issues by national educational policies, plans, and standards by exercising Authority, Responsibility, and Accountability (AuRA). Thus, the effectiveness of the School Head determines whether the school succeeds or fails.

Master Teachers are more successful in learning environments because they have a variety of vital leadership abilities. Master Teachers create a sense of community while achieving academic objectives. They exhibit emotional intelligence, foster kindness, and respect, and provide a secure and friendly learning atmosphere. They also serve as school policies, processes, practices, and collective accountability guidelines. To evaluate instructional strategies and resource quality, master teachers also need to possess stronger analytical skills. Within the parameters of their mandate, they must push educators to actively suggest higher-order thinking abilities and reflective activities. They also need to be extremely flexible, especially when it comes to changing the curriculum to reflect changes in how society is moving forward. Master Teachers must develop their accountability, initiative, and support for teacher development skills. MTs are expected to bring people together—individuals, groups, communities, and stakeholders—around common causes and objectives as skilled communicators. Their leadership abilities must include active listening, mediation, and conflict-resolution techniques (Tanguay, 2022).

Communicating ideas, facts, and feelings to the learning environment is another crucial leadership trait for Master Teachers. They need to be proficient communicators because good interpersonal relationships depend on it. They also have decisions on the building needs, resources, and curriculum. Making decisions continually is part of their job description as they collaborate with educators, parents, students, and other administrators to determine what is best for everyone.

As leaders in the classroom, Master Teachers are responsible for monitoring the classroom, providing examples, holding conferences, holding seminars, microteaching, moderating test questions, and moderating marking schemes. Checks are also made on the lesson plans, work schedules, student notes, teachers' timeliness, and regular attendance. To ensure that teachers utilize their skills when needed and that instruction and instructional practices are ultimately improved, the headmaster of the school, the instructors, and the department heads must be able to supervise these duties (Suele, et al, 2015).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study was anchored on the following theories: the Path-Goal Theory of Leadership by Robert J. House (1974), the Theory of Instructional Competence by Erik De Corte (1976), and the Theory of Performance by Richard Schechner (1985).

House's (1974) Theory of Leadership discusses supervision as a type of leadership. It suggests that master teachers, or other effective school leaders, should clarify the steps or routes their subordinates might take to improve job satisfaction and performance. Master teachers, who are members of the school leadership team by designation, have leadership abilities and practices that are primarily intended to direct teachers down the correct route so that they can accomplish the shared purpose. Related to this is the Master Teachers' mentorship program, in which junior teachers are expected to serve as the mentees.

Furthermore, De Corte's Theory of Instructional Competence sought to explain how to support individuals' learning and growth, foster environments that increase learning opportunities, and enhance instruction. This specific theory explores behaviorism, cognitive, and constructivist methods to explain how behavior responds to stimuli, delves into mental functions like memory and problem-solving, and strongly emphasizes active engagement, independent learning, and knowledge production. In conclusion, competence theory and instructional competence theory combine to improve teaching methods, create productive learning environments, and enable students to realize their greatest potential.

Lastly, performance theory has its roots in several disciplines, most notably in Richard Schechner's work (1985). This thesis highlighted how societies worldwide were performative, with daily life, rituals, and events guided by a performance code. Through ethnographic research conducted in many civilizations and circumstances, these writers

emphasized the importance of performance in understanding human behavior. According to performance theory, each one of us acts in our society.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the levels of leadership skills and instructional competence of Master Teachers in a medium-sized Division in a fourth-class component city in Central Philippines in relation to teachers' performance during School Year 2022-2023. Furthermore, this study sought to determine: 1) the level of leadership skills of Master Teachers in monitoring and evaluation and curriculum enhancement; 2) the level of instructional competence of Master Teachers in teaching approaches and strategies and management of learning environment; 3) the level of leadership skills of Master Teachers when grouped according to age, educational attainment, length of service, and Monthly income; 4) the level of instructional competence of Master Teachers when grouped according to the above demographics; 5) the level of performance of teachers when grouped according to the same demographics; 6) the significant difference in the level of leadership skills of Master Teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned demographics; 7) the significant difference in the level of instructional competence of Master Teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned demographics; 8) the significant difference in the performance of teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned demographics; 9) the significant relationship between the leadership skills of MTs and teachers' performance; and 10) the significant relationship between the instructional competence of MT's and teachers' performance.

Research Methodology:

This section provides information on how the study was conducted, allowing readers and other researchers to evaluate and replicate the research, and contributes to the overall rigors and credibility of the research findings.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design deemed relevant and appropriate in determining the leadership skills and instructional competence of Master Teachers in relation to teachers' performance. Dudovskiy (2017) stated that descriptive research design attempts to determine, describe, or identify characteristics found within the phenomena investigation. In line with the present study, it is the nature of this undertaking to determine the conditions of things in their present state.

Respondents

The study's respondents were 204 public elementary school teachers from a total population of 430. Since the number of respondents is quite large, stratified sampling and random sampling techniques were used using Cochran formula to find the sample size. To get the percentage, the respondents from each section were divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size. The researcher will randomly select the respondents from each section using the lottery technique.

Instruments

This study used a self-made questionnaire with 40-line items to gather data from the teachers who served as respondents. The instrument was subjected to validity (4.93 - excellent) and reliability tests (0.981 for leadership skills, and 0.966 for instructional competence, both interpreted as good). The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part intended to gather the socio-economic profile of the respondents, and the second part contained the 40-line items for the questionnaire part. There were 20-line items for leadership skills and 20 for instructional competence.

Data Collection

After establishing the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researcher submitted a letter request to the Schools Division Superintendent asking permission to conduct the study within a specified period outside of school hours. After securing the approval, the same letter was distributed to the school heads, the questionnaires were distributed, and the same were retrieved after three days for recording. The responses were encoded and subjected to data analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Likewise, statistical tables were constructed per consideration of the objectives stated in this study. The results were presented according to the sequence of the objectives.

Data Analysis & Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1 to 6 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as statistical tools to determine MT's leadership skills and instructional competence. Objectives 7 to 9 used a comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test statistical tools to establish the significant difference in MT's leadership skills, Instructional Competence, and Teachers'

Performance. Objectives 10 to 11 used relational analysis and Spearman rho as statistical tools to determine the significant relationship between MTs leadership skills and instructional competence with teachers' performance.

Ethical Considerations

This study earmarked and minimized potential risks of harm to its target respondents by ensuring that all of the gathered data, respondents' profile and responses were treated with full confidentiality and solely used for this study. The researcher equally secured the respondents' free and prior informed consent and assured them of their right to withdraw from research participation if necessary.

Results and Discussions

This section presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered to find answers to the objectives of the research paper. This section demonstrates the rigor and validity of the findings and contributes to the broader body of knowledge in this field.

Leadership Skills of Master Teachers

Table 1

Level of leadership skills of Master Teachers in Monitoring and Evaluation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The Master Teacher ...		
1. holds meetings and discuss grade level issues regularly.	4.56	Very High Level
2. assist in evaluating the performance of teachers.	4.71	Very High Level
3. leads in conducting FGDs to discuss critical issues in school.	4.61	Very High Level
4. remind teachers of key rule-out and deliverables for compliance.	4.67	Very High Level
5. provide timely, accurate and specific feedback in collegial manner to teachers regarding performance	4.62	Very High Level
6. conducts FGD with teachers regularly to assess pupils' learning needs.	4.61	Very High Level
7. constantly monitor teachers' teaching needs.	4.53	Very High Level
8. provides feedback to School Head on teachers' & learners' needs.	4.60	Very High Level
9. assesses overall academic operations to know where to help	4.50	Very High Level
10. determines the classroom needs of teachers.	4.51	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.59	Very High Level

Table 1 shows the leadership skills of MTs in monitoring and evaluation with an overall mean of 4.59, interpreted to mean very high level (VHL).

Item No. 2 which states that "The Master Teacher assist in evaluating the performance of teachers" got the highest mean score of 4.71. In contrast, Item No. 9 which states that "The Master Teacher assesses overall academic operations to know where to help" got the lowest mean score of 4.50. This implies that few teachers believe that some MT's are less involved in overseeing academic operations to ensure that teachers are guided where and how to provide help to learners. This conclusion contradicts the findings of Namunga's (2017) investigation into the effects of instructional practice monitoring on teaching and learning. The study employed a mixed-methods approach with a descriptive survey design. Glatthorn's concept of differentiated supervision, which promotes diverse supervisory techniques based on the scenario, served as the study's foundation. The study found a significant relationship between teaching strategies and supervision. The observation of instructional methods was therefore determined to significantly impact the teaching and learning processes in secondary schools in Bungoma County. The results imply that raising the quality of instructional supervision could improve student achievement.

Table 2

Level of Leadership Skills of Master Teachers in Curriculum Enhancement

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The Master Teacher...		
1. closely work with teachers in discussing curriculum to enhance teaching competencies.	4.63	Very High Level
2. leads in the preparation of learning materials, localizing and in contextualizing the curriculum.	4.55	Very High Level
3. helps implement the measures by the School's Division to enhance teaching-learning experiences.	4.53	Very High Level
4. create programs that enhances the delivery of curriculum content.	4.57	Very High Level

5. discuss curriculum goals in relation with teaching strategies with new teachers.	4.58	Very High Level
6. develop strategies that will help foster learning absorption.	4.55	Very High Level
7. trains younger teachers with effective teaching skills.	4.62	Very High Level
8. interprets salient curriculum areas to ensure that teachers are enlightened.	4.55	Very High Level
9. initiates group activities that intend to evaluate curriculum content to achieve academic goals	4.64	Very High Level
10. Help track teachers' teaching improvement skills to ensure that each one is aligned in using effective strategies.	4.67	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.59	Very High Level

Table 2 shows the leadership skills of MTs in curriculum enhancement with an overall mean of 4.59, interpreted to mean very high level (VHL).

Item No. 10 which state that "Master Teachers help track the teaching improvement skills of teachers to ensure that each one is aligned in using effective strategies got the highest mean score of 4.67, interpreted as "Very High Level," whereas, Item No. 3 which states that "Master Teachers helps implement the measures being implemented by the School's Division to enhance teaching-learning experiences" got the lowest mean score of 4.53, interpreted as "Very High Level." The lowest mean score is still very high, and this may not necessarily indicate a problem or an issue, however, being the lowest mean, this indicates the area which may need further improvement. As it appeared in this result, some teachers believe there is a need for MTs to be visibly involved in putting measures that will help improve teachers' experiences in teaching, and learners in studying, particularly with curriculum enhancement. The Office of Education Research, the National Institute of Education, and Nanyang Technological University in Singapore have all conducted classroom pedagogy research in Singapore, producing significant outcomes in Singapore's conventional classroom practices.

Instructional Competence of Master Teachers

Table 3

Level of Instructional Competence of Master Teachers in Terms of Teaching Approaches

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The Master Teacher...		
1. closely work with teachers in discussing curriculum to enhance teaching competencies.	4.63	Very High Level
2. leads in the preparation of learning materials, localizing and in contextualizing the curriculum.	4.55	Very High Level
3. helps implement the measures by the School's Division to enhance teaching-learning experiences.	4.53	Very High Level
4. create programs that enhances the delivery of curriculum content.	4.57	Very High Level
5. discuss curriculum goals in relation with teaching strategies with new teachers.	4.58	Very High Level
6. develop strategies that will help foster learning absorption.	4.55	Very High Level
7. trains younger teachers with effective teaching skills.	4.62	Very High Level
8. interprets salient curriculum areas to ensure that teachers are enlightened.	4.55	Very High Level
9. initiates group activities that intend to evaluate curriculum content to achieve academic goals	4.64	Very High Level
10. Help track teachers' teaching improvement skills to ensure that each one is aligned in using effective strategies.	4.67	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.59	Very High Level

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Item No. 10 which state that "Master Teachers help track the teaching improvement skills of teachers to ensure that each one is aligned in using effective strategies got the highest mean score of 4.67, interpreted as "Very High Level," whereas, Item No. 3 which states that "Master Teachers helps implement the measures being implemented by the School's Division to enhance teaching-learning experiences" got the lowest mean score of 4.53, interpreted as "Very High Level."

The lowest mean score is still very high and this may not necessarily indicate a problem or an issue, however, being the lowest mean, this indicates the area which may need further improvement. As it appeared in this result,

some teachers believe there is a need for MTs to be visibly involved in putting measures that will help improve teachers' experiences in teaching and learners' studying, particularly with curriculum enhancement.

The Office of Education Research, the National Institute of Education, and Nanyang Technological University in Singapore have all conducted classroom pedagogy research in Singapore, producing significant outcomes in Singapore's conventional classroom practices. Ng (2019) corroborated this result with his study results. Additionally, he underlined that five notable instructional leadership techniques were recognized in their local context. These practices are as follows: first, principals of elementary schools showed ongoing instructional leadership. Secondly, there are instructional leaders all over the place. Third, there seems to be a greater variety of instructional leadership domains available to principals. Fourth, the national contextual uniqueness of the state of Singapore tends to correspond with instructional leadership. Fifth, school heads may embrace the instructional objectives of their predecessors if they remain relevant.

Table 4
Level of Instructional Competence of Master Teachers in Terms of Management of Learning Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The Master Teacher ...		
1. provides support to the School Head in implementing school policies, in monitoring and assessing school operations.	4.75	Very High Level
2. helps build the confidence of teachers and create opportunities for stakeholders to support teachers.	4.75	Very High Level
3. support the Scool Head in planning and implementing school improvement program.	4.75	Very High Level
4. takes the lead in creating a school environment conducive for learning and safety for teachers.	4.71	Very High Level
5. facilitates the collaboration of parents and teachers.	4.68	Very High Level
6. supports the creation of a harmonious relationship between teachers, school heads and supervisors.	4.60	Very High Level
7. creates opportunities for collaborative efforts between school and the community.	4.65	Very High Level
8. embarks on a bridging role between stakeholders and the school to facilitate faster school support.	4.62	Very High Level
9. takes the lead in the confidence building of teachers and school staffs.	4.75	Very High Level
10. suggests activities to the SH that will help foster a conducive working environment for teachers.	4.79	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.71	Very High Level

Table 4 shows the leadership skills of MTs in learning environment with an overall mean of 4.71, interpreted to mean very high level (VHL).

Item No. 10 which states that "The Master Teacher suggests activities to the SH that will help foster a conducive working environment for teachers" got the highest mean score of 4.79, interpreted as "very high level." Meanwhile, Item No. 6, which states that "The Master Teacher supports the creation of a harmonious relationship between teachers, school heads and supervisors," got the lowest mean score of 4.60, interpreted as "very high level."

Once more, the lowest mean score appeared to be on a "very high level," and rather than seeing this as a problem, this is viewed entirely as an opportunity for MTs to improve their engagement in programs that seek to have a common understanding between stakeholders in the school, particularly between teachers and the high ranking officers of the school or district.

The results of Jimenez's (2023) study on the instructional leadership of school heads, which assessed teachers' work performance, emotional competencies, and instructional leadership skills in a sample of public junior high schools in the City Schools Division of Biñan City for the school year 2021–2022, confirmed this outcome. The results demonstrated that school administrators possessed very high levels of both emotional and instructional leadership competencies. 206 of the respondents obtained an IPCRF work performance grade of Outstanding for their teachers' work performance. The results also showed a strong correlation between the emotional competencies of the school head and their degree of instructional leadership abilities. The results showed that the work performance of teachers and the instructional leadership proficiency of the school head were significantly correlated. The findings showed that there was little correlation between the emotional intelligence of school administrators and the work performance of teachers. The work performance of the instructors and the school heads' emotional competency levels did not significantly correlate. In order to improve the school heads' emotional intelligence, instructional leadership abilities, and rapport-building with teachers, an action plan was suggested.

Teachers' Performance

Table 5
Level of Performance of Teachers when Grouped according to Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, and Length of Service

Variable	Category	Mean	Interpretation
Age	Younger	4.80	Outstanding
	Older	4.83	Outstanding
Educational Attainment	Lower	4.83	Outstanding
	Higher	4.80	Outstanding
Length of Service	Shorter	4.80	Outstanding
	Longer	4.83	Outstanding
Family Income	Lower	4.81	Outstanding
	Higher	4.82	Outstanding

Despite the fact that teachers' performance was "Outstanding there is a wider room for improvement for teachers' performance. The way teachers behave in the classroom has a big impact on how well their students learn. It is the work a teacher does inside the educational system during a specific time period to accomplish organizational objectives. Instructors combine their expertise, talents, and knowledge to create specialized performance competencies that serve as catalysts for students' academic success. Usop (2015) observed that teachers who are happy in their roles continue to perform at a high standard. Teachers that are happy in their jobs are also productive employees (Miñon, 2017).

Comparative Analysis in the level of MT's Leadership skills in terms of Curriculum enhancement, and Teaching Approaches and Strategies when grouped and compared according to variables

Table 6
Difference in the Level of Leadership Skills of Master Teachers in Terms of Curriculum Enhancement According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	102	107.77	4664.500	0.185	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	102	97.23				
Educational Attainment	Lower	129	105.57	4442.000	0.312	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	75	97.23				
Length of Service	Shorter	102	109.24	4515.000	0.090	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	102	95.76				
Family Income	Lower	106	107.15	4701.500	0.224	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	98	97.47				

All of the p-values were higher than the significant level of 0.05, thus the results were concluded as not significant. This implies that regardless of their categories where they belong, the opinion of the teachers in assessing the leadership skills of MTs were almost the same. This also means that age, Educational Attainment, length of service and Family Income have no significant impact in the opinion of the respondents in assessing MT's leadership skills. This further means that there is no disagreement between the opinion of the respondents, and without undue resistance, it would be easier to align teachers with future programs that will be managed or implemented by MTs themselves.

Table 7
Difference in the Level of Instructional Competence of Master Teachers in Teaching Approaches and Strategies According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	102	106.19	4825.500	0.340	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	102	98.81				
Educational Attainment	Lower	129	101.95	4767.000	0.853	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	75	103.44				
Length of Service	Shorter	102	108.22	4618.500	0.139	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	102	96.78				
Family Income	Lower	106	107.84	4627.500	0.151	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	98	96.72				

All of the p-values were higher than the significant level of 0.05, thus the results were concluded as not significant. This indicates the uniformity of opinion among and between respondents regardless of their groupings. This equally provides an insight that it will be smoother to implement MT-led programs in the future because the respondents are highly trusting of their instructional competence and skills.

Relational analysis

This section provides information on whether a significant relationship exists between MT's leadership skills and instructional competence and teachers' performance.

Table 8
Relationships Between the Leadership Skills and Instructional Competence of MT's and Teachers' Performance

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Leadership Skills				
Teacher's Performance	0.096	0.173	0.05	Not Significant
Instructional Competence				
Teacher's Performance	0.074	0.295	0.05	Not Significant

Leadership Skills: This is plainly indicative of the fact that no matter how low or high the level of MT's leadership skills, teachers are dutybound to perform on their own. While it is true that MT's leadership skills may impact teachers' performance, the results shown in this table prove that even in the absence of such leadership, the teachers will always perform.

Instructional Competence: The table shows that competent or less competent teachers will surely deliver on their mandate to provide quality education to learners. On the one hand, this is not to dispel whatever positive contribution of MT's instructional competence on teachers' performance; yes, there could be. However, based on the results shown in Table 30, it proved otherwise.

Conclusion

The very high level of leadership skills of Master Teachers can be attributed to the high engagement of Master Teachers, which makes them more visible as school leaders in many aspects. This is also because many School Heads entrust some obligations to Master Teachers, training them to be more skilled in leadership. The instructional competence of Master Teachers is also very high because, by normal standards, Master Teachers are classroom teachers, and their ability to see classroom processes is based on firsthand experiences. Master Teacher's competence as instructional leaders must indeed be formidable and truthful. There was no significant relationship between the leadership skills of Master Teachers and teachers' performance. This accounts for the fact that teachers are independent workers, and

they deliver good output with or without Master Teachers' supervision and technical assistance. This is a positive thing to observe because not all the time that Master Teachers are available to help teachers. There was no significant relationship between the instructional competence of Master Teachers and teachers' performance which means that even if the Master Teachers assigned fell short of the needed competence, the ability of the teachers to provide quality education is always there.

Acknowledgment

This study was made possible through the support, guidance, and encouragement of the following mentors: Dr. Lilybeth P. Eslabon, Dr. Rey T. Eslabon, Dr. Randolph L. Asistido, Dr. Ma. Leni C. Francisco, and Dr. Mima M. Villanueva. Thank you for your assistance.

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